

Synthesis of Some Pyrimidine Derivatives

K. A. THAKAR and C. H. GILL

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004

Manuscript received 2 July 1982, accepted 30 May 1983

Several new 2-amino- and 2(1H)-thiopyrimidine derivatives are synthesised by condensing flavones with guanidine and thiourea, respectively in alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution. These are characterised by chemical and ir spectral analysis. Antifungal and antialgal activities of some of these compounds are evaluated.

CERTAIN pyrimidine derivatives are known to possess anticancer activity¹⁻⁵. Various 4,6-diphenyl-2(1H)-thiopyrimidines and 4,6-diphenyl 2-aminopyrimidines are found to be associated with antitumor activity⁶⁻¹⁰. In view of this, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise variously substituted 4,6-diphenyl-2(1H)-thio and 2-amino pyrimidine derivatives and test them for their biological activity.

Flavones (I), reported by us earlier¹¹, on condensation with thiourea⁶ in alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution yielded 6-(*o*-hydroxy substituted phenyl)-4-(substituted phenyl)-2(1H)-thiopyrimidines (II), and on condensation with guanidine⁶ gave 6-(*o*-hydroxy substituted phenyl)-4-(substituted phenyl)-2-aminopyrimidines (III).

IR spectra (nujol) of 2(1H)-thiopyrimidines (II) showed bands at 3200 cm^{-1} (ν -NH), 1220 cm^{-1} (ν C=S), 1600 cm^{-1} (ν C=N) and 1460 cm^{-1} (ν -N-C=S group¹²) and ir spectra (KBr) of 2-aminopyrimidines (III) showed bands at 3455 cm^{-1} , 3320 cm^{-1} (-NH asymmetric and symmetric stretch), 1620 cm^{-1} (-NH bending vibration), 1290 cm^{-1} (C-N stretch) and 3200 cm^{-1} (OH phenolic).

Physical data of these compounds are recorded in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

TABLE 1—SUBSTITUTED 2(1H)-THIOPYRIMIDINES (II)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R'	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	220
2.	H	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	210
3.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	186
4.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	220
5.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	264
6.	H	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	220
7.	H	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	192
8.	H	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	228
9.	H	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	211
10.	H	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	225
11.	H	H	Br	2'-OCH ₃	185
12.	H	H	Br	3'-OCH ₃	214
13.	H	H	Br	4'-OCH ₃	240
14.	H	H	Br	2'-CH ₃	218
15.	H	H	Br	4'-CH ₃	221
16.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	200
17.	CH ₃	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	208
18.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	269
19.	OH	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	198
20.	OH	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	268
21.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	227
22.	H	CH ₃	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	274
23.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	261
24.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-CH ₃	202
25.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-CH ₃	290
26.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	224
27.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	210
28.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	228
29.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	200
30.	OH	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	240
31.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	185
32.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	238
33.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	288
34.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	230
35.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	210
36.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	235
37.	Cl	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	262
38.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	280
39.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	222
40.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	282
41.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-Cl	210
42.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-Cl	215
43.	H	H	Cl	2'-Cl	218
44.	H	H	Cl	4'-Cl	217
45.	H	H	Br	2'-Cl	230
46.	H	H	Br	4'-Cl	220
47.	OH	H	Cl	2'-Cl	205
48.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-Cl	234
49.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-Cl	210

(Table 1 Contd.)

50.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-Cl	228
51.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-Cl	215
52.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-Cl	210
53.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-Cl	270
54.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-Cl	252
55.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-Cl	295

All the compounds gave satisfactory analysis for C and H.

Solvents for crystallisation: Ethanol for Sl. No. 3; methanol for No. 34; pyridine for Nos. 5, 18, 22, 25, 32, 36-38, 40, 50 and AcOH for the rest

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTED-2-AMINOPYRIMIDINES (III)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R'	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	185
2.	H	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	275
3.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	220
4.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	110
5.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	212
6.	H	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	224
7.	H	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	268
8.	H	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	203
9.	H	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	177
10.	H	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	251
11.	H	H	Br	2'-OCH ₃	255
12.	H	H	Br	3'-OCH ₃	172
13.	H	H	Br	4'-OCH ₃	220
14.	H	H	Br	2'-CH ₃	187
15.	H	H	Br	4'-CH ₃	243
16.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	230
17.	CH ₃	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	235
18.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	255
19.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	130
20.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	262
21.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	210
22.	H	CH ₃	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	230
23.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	254
24.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-CH ₃	215
25.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-CH ₃	265
26.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	190
27.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	165
28.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	200
29.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	122
30.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	168
31.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	170
32.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	205
33.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	245
34.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	110
35.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	238
36.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	220
37.	Cl	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	210
38.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	279
39.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	110
40.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	275
41.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-Cl	238
42.	H	H	Cl	2'-Cl	220
43.	H	H	Cl	4'-Cl	256
44.	H	H	Br	2'-Cl	232
45.	H	H	Br	4'-Cl	242
46.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-Cl	200
47.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-Cl	254
48.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-Cl	224
49.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-Cl	135
50.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-Cl	285
51.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-Cl	225
52.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-Cl	260

All the compounds gave satisfactory analysis for C and H.

Solvents for crystallisation: Methanol for Sl. Nos. 1, 4, 14, 19, 24, 29, 31, 34, 35, 39; ethanol for 26, 42, 44, 49; methanol + AcOH for No. 28; ethanol + AcOH for 6, 7, 27, 32, 48; aq. pyridine for 12; benzene for 8 and AcOH for the rest.

Experimental

Synthesis of 6-(o-hydroxy substituted phenyl)-4-(substituted phenyl)-2(1H)-thiopyrimidines (II): A mixture of flavone (0.01 mole), thiourea (0.02 moles), KOH (0.02 moles; dissolved in a small amount of water) and alcohol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. The solution was then cooled and acidified with dil. HCl when a yellow solid was obtained. It was filtered and crystallised from proper solvent.

Synthesis of 6-(o-hydroxy substituted phenyl)-4-(substituted phenyl)-2-aminopyrimidines (III): A mixture of flavone (0.01 mole), guanidine hydrochloride (0.02 mole), potassium hydroxide (0.02 moles; dissolved in 2-3 ml of water) and methanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. The solution was cooled, diluted with water and acidified with acetic acid when a yellow solid precipitated out. It was filtered and crystallised from proper solvent.

Biological activity:

Some of the compounds were screened for anti-fungal and anti-algal activity.

Aspergillus flavus (an aflatoxin producing fungus) was chosen for antifungal screening. The compounds were tested by paper disc method¹⁸ at 100 ppm. None of the compounds showed any promising activity.

Nostoc sp. and *Tolypothrix teninus* were chosen for anti-algal screening. The compounds were tested at 100 ppm by paper disc method. None of the compounds showed any appreciable activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Shri R. S. Saler and C. B. Chaporkar, Institute of Science, Aurangabad, for biological screening of the compounds. One of the authors (C. H. G.) is thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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